

D5.1 – Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication

SYSAGE – Building Excellence in Systems Immunology and Healthy Ageing research

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SYSAGE

Building excellence in Systems Immunology and Healthy Ageing research

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A living document created to inform of the projects external communication and result dissemination and exploitation for stakeholders. In addition the document includes publication strategy for the project.

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Abbreviations

Acronym	Meaning
CEDP	Communication, Exploitation and Dissemination Plan
D	Deliverable
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
IP	Intellectual Property
IP	Institut Pasteur
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
M	Month
MS Teams	Microsoft Teams
OA	Open Access
UCPH	University of Copenhagen
UTARTU	University of Tartu
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

This document presents the Communication, Exploitation and Dissemination Plan (CEDP) for the SysAge project. The creation of this document is mandated by Work Package 5 (WP5) and is the first deliverable within that work package. The document outlines a structured approach to ensuring project visibility, knowledge transfer and engagement with key stakeholders while aligning with Horizon Europe guidelines. Additionally, it details the Publication Strategy (D5.3) for scientific articles produced during the project.

SysAge places a strong emphasis on external communication to maximize the impact and reach of its research activities. The strategies outlined in this document ensure that project findings are effectively shared with the scientific community, industry partners, policymakers, healthcare professionals and the general public.

This document exclusively addresses external communication. Internal communication between project members is covered separately under Deliverable D1.1 "D1.1-Project_Management_Plan_SysAge".

The document will be continuously updated throughout the project, culminating in a final report by M36 (August 2027) that summarizes the results of the communication, dissemination and exploitation and publication efforts.

1. Introduction

1.1. Project introduction

The SysAge project focuses on advancing research in systems immunology and healthy aging by enhancing the capabilities of Tartu University (UTARTU) through collaboration with Institut Pasteur (IP, France) and University of Copenhagen (UCPH, Denmark) under the Horizon Europe Twinning Initiative. With a duration of 36 months, spanning from September 2024 to August 2027. The SysAge project is structured around five interconnected Work Packages (WPs). Each WP is designed to achieve specific objectives while collectively driving the project towards its overarching goals. By the project's conclusion, SysAge aims to establish a foundation for sustainable, high-impact research collaborations and to elevate UTARTU's research profile in Europe.

1.2. Deliverable information

Within the SysAge project, Work Package 5 (WP5) – Networking, Dissemination and Communication focuses on effectively sharing project results with various external stakeholders. The first task under WP5 is to develop this Communication, Exploitation and Dissemination Plan (CEDP), referenced as Deliverable 5.1 (D5.1). UTARTU serves as lead of WP5. This document outlines target audiences, key messages, communication channels and planned actions to ensure effective knowledge transfer. Additionally, this document includes the Publication Strategy (D5.3). Due to its interconnected nature to the dissemination, communication and exploitation activities.

The first version of this document must be submitted by Month 6 (February 2025), ensuring that dissemination and communication strategies are well-defined early in the project lifecycle. The document will be updated regularly throughout the project, making it a living document. With final update in M36 (August 2027) summarizing the results of communication, dissemination and exploitation and publication efforts.

1.3. Explanation of Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

Before continuing with strategies for communication, exploitation and dissemination, it is important to clarify their definitions and scope according to the European Research Executive Agency. These efforts are mandatory for the participants of the Horizon Europe programme.

EUROPEAN UNION #HorizonEU

COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION & EXPLOITATION WHAT IS THE DIFFERENCE AND WHY THEY ALL MATTER

Communication	Dissemination	Exploitation
Inform, promote and communicate activities and results	Make knowledge and results publicly available free-of-charge	Make concrete use of results for commercial, societal and political purposes
For whom Citizens, stakeholders and the media	For whom For those who can learn and benefit from the results, such as: scientists, industry, public authorities, policymakers, civil society	For whom For those who can take the results forward or invest in them, such as: researchers, stakeholders, industry (also SMEs), public authorities, policymakers, civil society
How <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Having a well-designed strategy ✓ Conveying clear messages ✓ Using the right channels 	How Publishing results in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Scientific magazines ✓ Scientific and/or targeted conferences ✓ Databases 	How <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Creating roadmaps, prototypes, software ✓ Sharing knowledge, skills, data
When From the start until the end of the action	When <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Anytime, as soon as results become available ✓ Up to four years after the end of the project 	When <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Towards the end of the action and beyond, as soon as exploitable results are available ✓ Up to four years after the end of the project
Why <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Engage with stakeholders ✓ Attract the best experts ✓ Raise awareness of how public money is spent ✓ Show the success of European collaboration 	Why <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Maximise the impact of the action ✓ Allow other researchers to go a step forward ✓ Contribute to the advancement of world class knowledge ✓ Make scientific results a common good 	Why <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Lead to new legislation or recommendations ✓ For the benefit of innovation, the economy and society ✓ Help to tackle a problem and respond to an existing demand
It is a legal obligation! Article 17 of Horizon Europe Grant Agreement	It is a legal obligation! Article 17 of Horizon Europe Grant Agreement	It is a legal obligation! Annex 5: Specific Rules and Article 16 of Horizon Europe Grant Agreement

Figure 1. Communication, dissemination & exploitation: what is the difference and why they all matter. Publications Office of the European Union, 2023, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2848/289075>

1.3.1. Communication

Communication refers to the process of promoting the project and its activities to a broad audience, including the general public. This ensures that the SysAge project gains visibility beyond the scientific community and reaches individuals who may not necessarily have prior knowledge of the research being conducted.

Communication efforts involve sharing information about the project's objectives, progress and outcomes through various media, including websites, press releases and social media platforms. But also includes various public events and open science initiatives that help raise awareness.

1.3.2. Dissemination

Dissemination focuses on sharing research results with specific audiences who can directly benefit from or build upon them, such as other researchers, industry professionals and policymakers. The goal of dissemination is to ensure that scientific advancements generated within the SysAge project are accessible and available for further use in academic, industrial, or regulatory contexts.

To effectively disseminate knowledge, SysAge will only publish in open-access scientific journals, give oral or poster presentations at conferences, participate in or organize workshops and the shares datasets through repositories. In addition Policy briefs also serve as key dissemination channels. Effective dissemination supports long-term collaboration, knowledge transfer and the development of new research initiatives and policies based on the project's results.

1.3.3. Exploitation

Exploitation refers to the process of ensuring that the results and outcomes of the SysAge project are put to practical use beyond its duration. This includes applications in further research, commercial development and policy implementation.

One of the key aspects of exploitation is identifying and protecting valuable research outputs that may be commercially viable through IP (*Intellectual Property*). This can include patent applications, licensing agreements and collaborations with industry partners to develop new products or services based on the project's findings. Additionally, exploitation involves integrating the research into educational programs,

clinical practices and regulatory frameworks to ensure that the knowledge generated within SysAge has a lasting impact on society.

2. Communication

2.1. Strategy for communication

The communication approach for SysAge emphasizes proactive, targeted and interactive engagement with diverse stakeholder groups. Regular updates will be disseminated through various channels such as, social media platforms – including the [SysAge LinkedIn page](#), [SysAge Instagram](#) and the [SysAge Website](#). These updates will keep stakeholders informed about project milestones, research findings and upcoming events. Timely press releases and media outreach will highlight major achievements and ensure broader visibility in the public sphere.

Messages will be carefully tailored to resonate with specific target groups. For academic audiences, the communication will utilize precise scientific language, while content intended for the general public will be simplified to enhance accessibility and understanding. The strategy will leverage a mix of traditional and digital media, including scientific publications, conferences, social media posts and public events, to maximize reach and engagement. Visual elements like infographics will be used to make complex information more digestible and engaging.

Consistency in branding and messaging is essential to maintaining a strong and recognizable identity across all communication materials. To ensure a cohesive and professional appearance, all outputs will adhere to the SysAge Style Guide, which defines the project's visual identity, tone and formatting standards. This unified approach will reinforce SysAge's presence across various platforms and audiences. Additionally, communication efforts will align with Horizon Europe's guidelines, emphasizing open science principles, transparency and societal impact. By highlighting SysAge's contributions to healthy aging research, the communication strategy will not only enhance visibility but also foster greater public engagement and scientific collaboration.

2.2. Stakeholders

SysAge communication efforts will focus on engaging various key stakeholders using different channels to maximize the projects impact and ensure research results reach relevant audiences.

2.2.1. Scientific Community

This group includes researchers and professionals in systems immunology, bioinformatics and aging-related fields. Communication efforts will focus on sharing research findings, fostering our collaborations and supporting interdisciplinary discussions through scientific conferences, open-access publications and FAIR data sharing.

2.2.2. PhD Students and Postdocs

Early-career researchers are a crucial target group, as they will contribute to the project's future impact. SysAge will engage them through research training opportunities, workshops, mentorship programs and invitations to participate in international research networks.

2.2.3. Potential Users of Research Results

This includes industry partners, biotechnology companies and pharmaceutical firms interested in utilizing the findings of the SysAge project. The communication strategy will involve targeted outreach to foster industry-academic partnerships and encourage technology transfer and commercialization of research results.

2.2.4. General Public

As aging and immunology are topics of broad societal interest, engaging the general public is key to fostering awareness of the project's impact. SysAge will use popular science articles, social media campaigns and public lectures to make research findings accessible to non-specialist audiences.

Table 1. Overview of the stakeholders for SysAge

Stakeholder group	Specific interests	Engagement approach	Key messages
Scientific Community	Advancing research in systems immunology and aging	Publications, conferences, collaborative research	Sharing research findings and fostering collaboration
PhD students, postdocs	Training, mentorship and networking opportunities	Workshops, training sessions, mentorship programs	Building future research capacity
Policymakers and Regulators	Informing health policy and funding decisions	Policy briefs, stakeholder meetings, advisory panels	Supporting evidence-based policy
Biotech Industry	Applying research findings to develop products and technologies	Networking events, direct outreach	Promoting commercialization and technology transfer
Healthcare Professionals	Translating research outcomes into clinical practice	Guidelines, continuing education programs	Enhancing patient care through research
General Public	Understanding the societal impact of aging	Raising awareness and promoting public engagement	Importance of healthy ageing research

2.3. Key Messages

The following key messages will guide SysAge's communication efforts, ensuring clarity, consistency and alignment with the project's goals:

1. **Advancing Healthy Aging:** SysAge is pioneering research in systems immunology to better understand and promote healthy aging.
2. **Collaborative Excellence:** Through partnerships with leading institutions like IP and UCPH,
3. **Enhancement of UTARTU's research capabilities:** SysAge aims to strengthen UTARTU's role as a leader in systems immunology and aging research.
4. **Interdisciplinary Research:** SysAge combines insights from various fields to tackle aging challenges.
5. **Empowering Science and Society:** SysAge's open science approach ensures that research findings benefit not only the scientific community but also policymakers and healthcare professionals

2.4. Contractual obligations

All communication activities within the SysAge project must adhere to the contractual obligations established under Horizon Europe funding regulations, as specified in the grant agreement (GA). These obligations ensure transparency, proper acknowledgment of funding sources and compliance with EU visibility guidelines.

The project is required to acknowledge funding by the European Union in all public-facing materials such as but not limited to: publications, press releases, presentations and digital content. This is achieved by prominently displaying the official EU emblem alongside the funding acknowledgment statement.

To simplify communication efforts, the emblem design has been updated to include both the funding acknowledgment and the grant number, ensuring consistency and compliance across all materials. These have been uploaded to the projects shared MS Teams folder and are accessible to people involved in the project.

Figure 2. First version of the EU emblem, that includes funding acknowledgement with detailed information about the grant agreement and the number

Figure 3. Second version of the EU emblem, that includes funding acknowledgement with only the grant agreement number.

2.5. Communication Tools

SysAge will implement a diverse range of communication tools to ensure effective outreach, engagement and visibility. These tools are selected to target specific stakeholder groups and to support the projects communication objectives.

Table 2. Overview of communication tools used by SysAge

Tool	Purpose	Target Audience
Website	Information about the project	All interested stakeholders
LinkedIn	Professional networking and engagement	Researchers, policymakers, industry partners
Instagram	Community engagement and visual storytelling	Community engagement and visual storytelling
Press Release	Public awareness and media engagement	General public and policymakers
Workshops	Knowledge transfer and skill development	Researchers, PhD students
Conferences	Research dissemination and collaboration	Scientific community, industry stakeholders
Public Events	Outreach to general public	General public, students

2.5.1. Website

A dedicated SysAge project website ([SysAge Website](#)) serves as the central hub for all project-related information. The website will be updated throughout the project. The website provides coverage of the project's mission, objectives and progress. It offers insights into SysAge's work packages and later on methodologies used, highlighting the collaborative efforts and scientific advancements achieved.

Although newsletters have not yet been established, the project team is considering their implementation as a means to regularly update stakeholders, subscribers and the general public about major project milestones and results.

Figure 4. Screenshot of SysAge Website Homepage from February 2025

2.5.2. Social Media Platforms

SysAge actively engages on social media to reach broader audiences and disseminate project results effectively. Social media plays a crucial role in engaging stakeholders, promoting events and sharing scientific knowledge in an accessible format.

The content strategy for SysAge focuses on:

- **Research:** Sharing major scientific achievements, publications and project milestones.
- **Behind-the-Scenes Content:** Offering a glimpse into lab work, team activities and day-to-day project developments to humanize the research.

- Educational Posts: Infographics and animations to make complex scientific concepts more digestible.
- Event Promotions: Announcements of conferences, workshops, webinars and public outreach events.
- Special Awareness Posts: Highlighting significant days and events to raise awareness and align with global conversations.

The Social Medias where SysAge is active are Instagram and LinkedIn. Posts will be tailored to each platform, making sure they are of interest to stakeholders active on those platforms. The post captions will make use of relevant hashtags and #HorizonEurope.

Table 3. SysAge Social Media platforms

Platform	Purpose	Content types	Stakeholders	Link
LinkedIn	Professional networking and engagement with the scientific community, policymakers and industry partners	Research highlights, event announcements, collaboration opportunities	Researchers, policymakers, industry partners	SysAge LinkedIn
Instagram	Community engagement and Visual storytelling	Images and videos from lab activities, team events, scientific infographics, interactive stories	General public, students, early-career researchers	SysAge Instagram

Figure 5. Screenshots from SysAge social media platforms as on February 2025. LinkedIn (left), Instagram (right)

2.5.3. Workshops

A series of training and industry-focused workshops will be organized in collaboration with project partners, ensuring a wide range of expertise and perspectives. Workshops are also an important part of SysAge's dissemination activities.

The training workshops are scheduled to take place in M12 (Aug 2025) and M24 (September 2026) of the project, focusing on systems immunology techniques, data analysis and collaborative research methodologies. These sessions will provide early-career researchers, PhD students and postdocs with hands-on training to enhance their skills.

The industry-focused workshops will be held in M18 (March 2026) and M30 (March 2027), designed to foster dialogue between researchers and industry stakeholders. These

workshops will explore potential applications of project findings, encourage technology transfer and promote collaboration opportunities.

A dedicated interdisciplinary workshop will be organized in M20 (May 2026), focusing on integrating diverse scientific fields to address complex challenges in systems immunology and healthy aging. This workshop will encourage cross-disciplinary collaborations and innovative approaches.

SysAge project members will consider participating in other workshops or webinar opportunities not set out in the proposal, should they arise. These opportunities have to be aligned with the projects goals. This approach allows the project to engage with existing scientific communities and maximize the impact of shared research.

To maximize engagement, all events will be actively promoted on SysAge's social media platforms. Coverage will include posts, stories and live updates during the events. Participants will be encouraged to share posts and stories on their personal networks, enhancing the visibility and reach of the events and fostering broader community engagement.

2.5.4. Press Releases and Media Engagement

SysAge will collaborate with media outlets to raise awareness of its milestones and engage the general public through targeted press releases to traditional media outlets, including major news agencies such as ERR News (Novaator). Press releases will cover significant project achievements, aiming to make complex scientific topics accessible and interesting to a wider audience. This approach will help ensure clarity and accuracy, fostering greater public interest and understanding. If needed we will work with communications specialist from the University of Tartu to ensure success when reaching out to Journalists.

SysAge has the possibility to publish articles in UTARTU's own newsletter, "*Universitas Tartuensis*", which is released 5 times per year and is available both online and in print form. While this offers an excellent opportunity to reach the academic and local community, the limitation is that articles are published exclusively in Estonian.

SysAge will also prepare Media Kits with visuals, fact sheets and expert contact information to support media outreach efforts. Project leaders and researchers will be available for interviews to appear in scientific magazines and general media, further promoting the project's activities and outcomes.

2.5.5. Conferences

SysAge has already participated in several international conferences, with plans to attend additional high-profile events in the future like international immunology conference. These conferences offer essential platforms to present research findings either via talks or poster presentations, share insights and engage with leading experts in the field. Participation in these events is crucial for attracting new researchers and fostering collaborations, potentially encouraging talented scientists to join UTARTU and contribute to the project's ongoing success. Conferences are also mentioned under dissemination strategy (3.2.).

2.5.6. Conferences Public Engagement Events

SysAge is committed to engaging with the general public through a variety of events. The project has already hosted multiple visits from schools, providing students with an introduction to systems immunology and healthy aging research. During these visits, students are introduced to the basics of immunology with content tailored to be age-appropriate and engaging. A tour of the lab is also provided, offering hands-on exposure to scientific work. The program is adaptable to the specific needs and interests of visiting schools, ensuring a meaningful and educational experience for all participants.

In addition to school visits, SysAge is working closely with the institute and university to participate in larger events, such as open days. These events provide an excellent opportunity to showcase the project's work to a broader audience and promote public interest in scientific research.

SysAge also plans to host its own dedicated public engagement event for world Immunology Day (April 29), bringing together researchers from UTARTU, students and the community to explore the project's findings and impact. This event will include presentations, discussions and hands-on activities to foster engagement and understanding.

2.6. Outcome of Communication activities

To ensure that SysAge's communication efforts are effective, the project will employ Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to monitor outreach, engagement and visibility across different platforms. These metrics will help assess the impact of communication activities and identify areas for improvement.

Table 4. Communication Activities expected outcome and KPIs

Communication Activity	KPI	Minimum Target (3 Years)	Evaluation Frequency
Website	Number of visitors, page views, Downloads	At least 500 visitors	Quarterly
Social Media	Engagement rate (likes, shares, comments), follower growth, post reach	At least 300 combined followers, Total Post reach of 1000	Monthly
Popular Science Press Releases	Number of articles published, media mentions, journalist engagement	At least 3 press articles published	Month after release
Workshops	Attendance numbers, participant feedback	At least 50 total attendees	After each Workshop
Conferences	Number of presentations given, audience engagement	At least 20 presentations given or posters presented	After each Conference
Public Engagement Events	Number of attendees, feedback from participants	At least 150 total attendees	After each Event

3. Dissemination

SysAge’s dissemination strategy is designed to ensure that the project’s results reach a broad audience, including the scientific community, industry stakeholders, policy makers and the general public. Dissemination is a continuous process throughout the project, beginning from the early stages and evolving as significant milestones are achieved. The dissemination process starts with the generation of research outputs, which are carefully documented and prepared for sharing with relevant stakeholders

SysAge’s dissemination strategy is dynamic and adaptable, allowing for adjustments based on feedback and emerging opportunities. Regular evaluations ensure that dissemination efforts remain effective and aligned with the project’s overarching goals of transparency, collaboration and societal impact.

Table 5. Overview of dissemination activities

Dissemination activity	Purpose	Target Audience
Scientific Publications	Share findings with academic community	Researchers, scholars, academic institutions
Conferences	Present research, build collaborations	Scientists, industry professionals, policymakers
Workshops	Train researchers, promote knowledge exchange	Early-career researchers, PhD students, postdocs
Online Platforms and website	Broaden reach of findings	Scientists, industry professionals, policymakers
Policy Briefs	Translate findings into actionable insights	Policymakers, regulatory bodies

3.1. Scientific Publications

Scientific publications are a primary means of disseminating SysAge’s research results, with results being submitted to high-impact, peer-reviewed and open-access journals. By targeting these kind of journals, SysAge ensures that its findings are accessible to a global network of experts. Additionally, open-access repositories are utilized to ensure that data and publications are freely available, promoting transparency and adherence to Horizon Europe’s open science policies.

3.2. Conferences

Conferences serve as another vital dissemination channel. SysAge actively participates in both national and international conferences, where project findings are presented to large audiences of researchers, clinicians and industry representatives. These conferences provide opportunities for networking, feedback and the exploration of new collaborative ventures.

Presenting at such events also enhances the visibility of SysAge, positioning the project as a leader in the field and attracting the interest of new researchers who may wish to join UTARTU or collaborate on future initiatives. Additionally, participation in workshops, roundtable discussions and industry networking sessions will facilitate knowledge transfer and strengthen academic and commercial partnerships. Conferences are also mentioned in chapter 2.5.5.

3.3. Workshops

Workshops and seminars are also integral to the dissemination strategy, offering forums where methodologies, results and future directions can be discussed in depth. These events are not only platforms for knowledge exchange but also opportunities to build lasting relationships with stakeholders who can benefit from or contribute to SysAge's and UTARTU's research. More details are found in chapter 2.5.3.

3.4. Online Platforms

Online platforms play a significant role in broadening the reach of dissemination activities. The SysAge project website serves as a central repository for research outputs, news and updates, ensuring that information is readily available to all interested parties. Social media channels complement the website by providing real-time updates, engaging content and facilitating direct interactions with the public.

3.5. Policy briefs

Policy briefs are developed to translate complex scientific findings into concise, actionable insights for policymakers. These documents highlight the most relevant results and their implications for public health and research funding, ensuring that SysAge's work informs decision-making processes at both national and European levels.

SysAge’s policy briefs will be tailored for various audiences, including government agencies, research councils, health organizations and EU policymakers. They will highlight key research findings, potential societal impacts and recommendations for integrating scientific advancements into policy frameworks. These briefs will also be presented in stakeholder meetings, advisory panels and research funding discussions to ensure maximum outreach and influence.

3.6. Outcome of Dissemination activities

The impact of SysAge’s dissemination activities will be assessed using Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to ensure effective knowledge transfer and stakeholder engagement. The following table outlines the KPIs and the minimum targets to be achieved during the three-year project duration

Table 6. Dissemination activity outcomes, KPIs and Minimum target

Communication Activity	KPI	Minimum Target (3 Years)	Evaluation Frequency
Scientific Publications	Number of peer-reviewed journal articles published	At least 1 publication	Annually
Conferences	Number of presentations given, audience engagement	At least 10 presentations given or posters presented	After each Conference
Workshops	Attendance numbers, participant feedback	At least 50 total attendees	After each Workshop
Website	Number of visitors, page views, Downloads	At least 500 visitors	Quarterly
Social Media	Engagement rate (likes, shares, comments), follower growth, post reach	At least 300 combined followers, Total Post reach of 1000	Monthly
Policy Briefs	Number of briefs published, engagement with policymakers	At least 1 policy brief issued	Annually

4. Publication Strategy

SysAge's publication strategy is designed to maximize research impact, ensure compliance with Horizon Europe's open science requirements and adhere to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data practices. The strategy prioritizes publishing in high-impact, peer-reviewed journals to enhance visibility and credibility within the scientific community. All publications will be submitted to fully Open Access journals that meet Horizon Europe's standards. Articles will be made freely available immediately upon publication, without embargo, ensuring compliance with the European Commission's policies on research transparency.

To align with FAIR data principles, research data will be properly managed, stored and shared in recognized repositories to promote transparency and reproducibility. More info on how that will be done can be found in D1.2 "D1.2_SysAge_DMP".

4.1. Target journals

Selecting appropriate journals is critical for reaching the intended audience while fulfilling open-access obligations. SysAge will target high-impact, open-access journals in systems immunology, aging research, bioinformatics and biomedical sciences. The following journals have been identified as suitable publication venues:

- **Frontiers in Immunology:** This journal focuses on all aspects of immunology and is fully open access. [Frontiers OA Policy](#)
- **Aging Cell:** This journal publishes research on the biology of aging and is fully open access. [Aging Cell OA Policy](#)
- **Clinical and Translational Medicine:** An open-access journal focusing on accelerating the translation of preclinical research to clinical applications. [Clinical and Translational Medicine OA Policy](#)
- **Cell Reports Medicine:** A fully open-access journal publishing research across the spectrum of biomedical sciences. [Cell Reports Medicine OA Policy](#)
- **Genome Biology:** This journal covers all areas of biology informed by genomic research and is fully open access. [Genome Biology OA Policy](#)
- **Genome Medicine:** An open-access journal focusing on the application of genetics and genomics to understand, diagnose and treat disease. [Genome Medicine OA Policy](#)

- **Open Research Europe Platform:** A publishing platform for Horizon Europe-funded research across all subject areas, ensuring immediate open access.

[Platform Link](#)

Publishing in these journals ensures maximum exposure, rapid dissemination and compliance with Horizon Europe's open science policies. All publications will be licensed under Creative Commons (CC BY), allowing for broad reuse and knowledge transfer.

To enhance early research dissemination, SysAge will also upload preliminary findings and manuscripts to preprint servers when allowed by journal policies. Preprint repositories such as bioRxiv, medRxiv, arXiv and Zenodo will be used to ensure timely sharing of results.

4.2. Collaborative Authorship and Ethical Considerations

SysAge fosters collaborative authorship across project partners to strengthen interdisciplinary research and ensure proper recognition of contributions from various institutions. Authors from UTARTU, Institut Pasteur and UCPH, along with additional collaborators, will be encouraged to co-author publications to highlight the joint effort and interdisciplinary nature of the project.

All publications must include proper acknowledgment of Horizon Europe funding and feature the required EU emblem to comply with funding obligations. Ethical integrity is paramount in research publishing and all authors will adhere to COPE (Committee on Publication Ethics) guidelines, ensuring the highest standards in research reporting. Measures will be taken to prevent plagiarism, data manipulation and authorship disputes, fostering responsible and transparent research dissemination. In accordance with FAIR principles, all publications will include a data availability statement, ensuring that datasets supporting published research are openly accessible through designated repositories.

5. Exploitation

The exploitation strategy for SysAge is designed to ensure that the research outcomes generated by the project are effectively translated into practical applications, societal benefits and industry advancements. The overarching objective is to ensure that the knowledge and innovations developed within SysAge contribute to healthcare improvements, industry-driven research, policy advancements and further scientific development beyond the project's duration. Steps in research exploitation will be made will full knowledge of the project partners and representatives of UTARTUS grant office

A key step in the exploitation process is the early identification and assessment of exploitable results. Throughout the project lifecycle, research outputs will be continuously monitored to determine their potential applications, commercial viability and societal impact and categorize them as such.

For Commercialization opportunities SysAge actively fosters collaborations with industry stakeholders to explore the opportunities and facilitate the transformation of research findings into market-ready solutions. Engagement with biotechnology, pharmaceutical and medical technology industries will be prioritized, with the aim of developing novel therapeutics, diagnostic tools and biomedical applications. Industry partnerships will be established through joint research initiatives and workshops. These collaborations will create new pathways for commercial investment, startup incubation and pilot studies that bridge the gap between academic research and real-world implementation. The project will also seek funding opportunities from innovation-driven programs, such as the European Innovation Council (EIC) and Horizon Europe innovation schemes, to support commercialization efforts should such discoveries be made.

If needed workshops and mentoring sessions will be organized to guide researchers through the commercialization process, offering insights into startup creation, technology transfer procedures and securing investment from venture capital funds. These initiatives will not only strengthen SysAge's impact within academia but also help bridge the gap between scientific discovery and real-world applications.

5.1. Management of IP

The project adheres to best practices for protecting intellectual assets, ensuring that research findings are appropriately safeguarded while also promoting open-access knowledge dissemination. IP protection measures include the use of patents, copyrights, trademarks and licensing agreements where applicable. Clear guidelines are

established for handling IP within the consortium, ensuring that contributions are properly attributed and that partners benefit fairly from the project's successes.

5.2. Outcome of Exploitation activities

The effectiveness of SysAge's exploitation strategy will be assessed using Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to measure the successful translation of research outputs into tangible applications. The following table outlines the expected outcomes over the three-year duration of the project.

Table 7. Exploitation Activities expected outcome and KPIs

Exploitation Activity	KPIs	Minimum Target	Evaluation Frequency
Workshop with Industry representatives	Number of commercial discussions	At least 2 workshops	Annually
Industry collaborations established	Number of industry partnerships and commercial discussions	3 Members of Industry attend the final conference	End of Project

5.3. Potential barriers exploitation

While the project's exploitation strategy is designed to be proactive and impactful, several potential barriers and challenges may arise. Identified risks and mitigation strategies include:

- **Regulatory and Compliance Barriers:** Research findings related to healthcare and pharmaceuticals may face complex regulatory approval processes before reaching market application. SysAge will work closely with regulatory experts and industry advisors to ensure compliance with EU medical regulations and international standards.
- **Market Readiness and Scalability:** Some research findings may require additional validation before becoming commercially viable. SysAge will seek proof-of-concept funding and pilot programs to accelerate readiness for industry adoption.
- **Limited Commercialization Experience:** Researchers may lack the necessary expertise in business development and startup creation. Targeted

entrepreneurship training and mentorship programs will be provided to overcome this challenge.

- **Financial Constraints for Industry Uptake:** Some technologies may require significant investment for full-scale development. SysAge will actively seek public-private partnerships and Horizon Europe innovation grants to support industrial scale-up.

By proactively addressing these potential barriers, SysAge aims to maximize the societal, industrial and economic impact of its research, ensuring that innovations developed within the project contribute to long-term advancements in healthcare, biotechnology and public policy.

6. Visual Identity

SysAge's visual identity is designed to ensure consistency and recognizability across all communication materials. A cohesive visual identity strengthens the project's brand, enhances its visibility and reinforces its credibility.

6.1. Logos

The SysAge logo is a central element of the visual identity, featuring an abstract hourglass symbol. This design conveys the project's focus on the passage of time and aging. The structures within the hourglass are antibodies, which are crucial components in immunology research. Their presence in the logo highlights the project's dedication to studying immune system processes.

The primary color used in the logo is a deep red, specifically hex #892020, which symbolizes life, health and vitality. This color reflects the project's focus on healthy aging and biomedical research, evoking associations with blood and medical science. The contrast between the bold red and the white or transparent background ensures high visibility and a modern, clean appearance suitable for various digital and print applications. To provide flexibility, the SysAge logo exists in three variations: the primary red version, as well as black and white alternatives. These variations allow for adaptability in different contexts, ensuring that the logo remains effective across various backgrounds and materials. The logo must always be displayed prominently and should not be distorted, recolored, or altered in any way that has not been approved. When used on digital platforms, it must maintain a resolution that ensures clarity and sharpness.

Figure 6. Primary logo of the SysAge project

Figure 7. Black and White versions of the SysAge logo

Typography is carefully selected to complement the visual identity, ensuring clarity and readability across different communication materials. The Atkinson Hyperlegible font is used in the SysAge logo, chosen for its high legibility and accessibility, making it suitable for broad audiences. For all official project documents, reports and templates, Aptos is the standard font. This modern and professional typeface maintains consistency and readability across all project communications, reinforcing a strong and unified brand image.

SysAge also incorporates the logos of its project partners in official documents. These logos are placed according to predefined layout guidelines to maintain a professional and balanced design. The positioning of partner logos ensures that all contributing organizations receive appropriate recognition while maintaining a cohesive visual structure.

Figure 8. Logo displayed from Consortium partner, University of Tartu

Figure 9. Logo displayed from Consortium partner, Institut Pasteur

Figure 10. Logo displayed from Consortium partner, University of Copenhagen

6.2. Templates

To maintain brand consistency, standardized templates are provided for different types of project documentation. Currently, SysAge has established templates for meeting minutes, official project documents and PowerPoint presentations. These templates incorporate the logo, color scheme and typography to ensure a cohesive look across all communication channels. Additional templates may be created as needed to support

evolving project requirements and maintain consistency in all external and internal communications.

DX.X - Name
SYSAGE - Building Excellence in Systems Immunology and Healthy Ageing research

This Project received funding from the European Union's HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-02-01 under grant agreement Nr. 101159920

Grant Agreement Number
101159920

This Project received funding from the HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-02-01 call

SYSAGE
 Building excellence in Systems Immunology and Healthy Ageing research

Work Package Nr.	WP Milestone Nr.	Title	Lead Beneficiary

Deliverable nature	Dissemination level	Status

Description of Document

Document review History		
Version	Author/Reviewer	Date

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Figure 11. Document Template for SysAge

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Minutes of meetings – SysAge

Date:
Location:

Participants:
UTARTU:
UCPH:
IP:
Agenda:
1.
2.
Action points:
UTARTU:
1.
IP:
1.
UCPH:
1.

1. Topic 1
Discussion details

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Participant list

Event - Name
Date: XX.XX.202X
Location:

	Full Name	Organization	Signature
1			
2			
3			
4			
5			
6			
7			
8			
9			
10			
11			
12			
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14			
15			
16			
17			

Figure 12. Minutes of Meetings Template for SysAge (left). Participant list template for SysAge (right)

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Title of presentation

Name
occupation

202X

Slide title

- Body text
- Copy this slide as needed

Project Nr. 101159920

101159920

Figure 13. PowerPoint template for SysAge

Visual guidelines dictate the correct use of the logo, including placement, sizing and color variations to ensure adaptability across different platforms and mediums. Adherence to these guidelines is mandatory for all project partners. All templates and logos are accessible to project partners via shared Teams. Regular reviews will be conducted to see if updates are needed to align with evolving communication needs and branding strategies.

7. Links

<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2848/289075>

<https://sisu.ut.ee/sysage/>

https://www.instagram.com/project_sysage/

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/project-sysage/?viewAsMember=true>

<https://www.frontiersin.org/about/open-access>

https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/page/journal/14749726/homepage/custom_copy.htm

<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/page/journal/20011326/article-publication-charges.html>

<https://www.cell.com/open-access>

<https://www.biomedcentral.com/about/open-access>

<https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>